

Establishment of Small Industrial Zones and Development of Their Marketing Activities: International Experiences

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada kichik va o'rta korxonalar faoliyatida tashkil etish va ularda marketingni rivojlanishi bo'yicha dunyoning yetakchi davlatlarining tajribasi ko'rib chiqiladi uni takomillashtirish bo'yicha xulosalar berilagan.

Kalit so'zlar: erkin iqtisodiy zonalar, kichik sanoat zonalari, biznes reja, marketing faoliyati, eksport, import, raqamli iqtisodiyot, soliq, elektron tijorat.

Аннотация . В диссертации рассмотрен опыт ведущих стран мира по организации деятельности малых и средних предприятий и развитию маркетинга в них, а также сделаны выводы по его совершенствованию.

Ключевые слова: свободные экономические зоны, малые промышленные зоны, бизнес-план, маркетинговая деятельность, экспорт, импорт, цифровая экономика, налог, электронная коммерция.

Abstract. The article examines the experience of the world's leading countries in the development of marketing in the activities of small and medium-sized enterprises, and offers suggestions for its improvement.

Keywords: free economic zones, small industrial zones, business plan, marketing activity, export, import, digital economy, tax, e-commerce.

Introduction

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 13, 2022, No. PF-153, "On Additional Measures to Increase the Efficiency of Special Economic, Small Industrial, Youth Industrial and Entrepreneurship Zones", specific tasks were defined to simplify the system of coordination and management of these zones, to improve conditions for attracting investments, to ensure the rapid implementation of investment projects, and thereby to create new jobs and increase the income of the population.

In addition, the Presidential Decree No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022, "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026", sets out tasks such as the

establishment of 200 new industrial zones and the development of a business incubator system in the regions.

Among the economists who have conducted theoretical research on the establishment and development of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and the organization of marketing activities in such enterprises are prominent scholars

such as I. Ansoff, B. Berman, G. L. Bagiev, P. S. Zavyalov, A. N. Romanov, V. Evans, J. J. Lamben, Ye. P. Golubkov, and F. Kotler. These figures have played a significant role in shaping modern marketing theory.

In Uzbekistan as well, the development of marketing science has been studied by scholars such as A. Soliyev, Sh. J. Ergashev, H. P. Abulqosimov, A. Bekmurodov, N. Q. Yuldashev, J. Jalolov, M. Qosimova, M. Yusupov, and many others.

Based on the objectives set out in the above-mentioned decrees of our President, the main methodological task today is to study the activities of small and medium-sized enterprises, to analyze international experience in developing marketing in these enterprises, to review scientific research conducted by economists, and to form necessary methodological recommendations suitable for the conditions of Uzbekistan.

Analysis

It is well known that the foundation of small industrial zones is composed mainly of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). As of today, there are **21 special economic zones (SEZs)**, **296 small industrial zones (SIZs)**, **23 technoparks**, and **494 clusters** in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The number of enterprises operating within them amounts to **689** in SEZs, **2,508** in SIZs, **1,178** in technoparks, and **499** in clusters.

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) — are companies that maintain their revenues, assets, or number of employees below a certain threshold. Compared to large corporations, SMEs are smaller organizations that create the majority of jobs in the global economy. Each country has its own specific definition of what constitutes a small or medium-sized enterprise. In addition to meeting size criteria, the sector of operation is also considered.

SMEs play a **crucial role** in the economy. They employ far more people than large firms and are generally more **entrepreneurial in nature**, helping to stimulate

innovation and flexibility in production and services. SMEs can exist in nearly every industry, though they are more likely to thrive in sectors requiring smaller initial investments and fewer employees. The most common types of SMEs worldwide include **manufacturing enterprises, service companies, law firms, dental offices, restaurants, and bars.**

SMEs in the United States

In the United States, the **Small Business Administration (SBA)** classifies small businesses according to ownership structure, number of employees, revenue, and industry. For instance, in manufacturing, an SME is defined as a company with **500 or fewer employees.** In contrast, mining companies engaged in copper or nickel extraction may have up to **1,500 employees** and still be considered SMEs. Similar to the European Union, the United States also classifies companies with **fewer than 10 employees** as **Small Office/Home Office (SOHO)** businesses.

When it comes to taxation, the **Internal Revenue Service (IRS)** does not explicitly distinguish between small and medium enterprises. Instead, it groups **small businesses and sole proprietors** separately from medium and large corporations. According to the IRS, a small business is one with **assets of \$10 million or less**, while a large enterprise has **more than \$10 million in assets.**

Based on recent data from the **SBA Office of Advocacy**, there are nearly **33.2 million small businesses** in the United States, 82% of which have **no employees.** Small businesses account for **99.9% of all firms, 99.7% of payroll-employing firms,** and **97.3% of exporters** in the U.S. economy.

However, SME ownership remains **disproportionately dominated by white males,** highlighting inequalities in access to financial and entrepreneurial resources. As of March 2023, only **19.6% of employer firms** were minority-owned, and **21.7%** were owned by women.

SMEs in Canada

The Government of Canada defines each business type based on the number of employees, according to Canadian industrial statistics:

- **Micro-enterprises:** 1–4 employees

- **Small enterprises:** 5–99 employees
- **Medium enterprises:** 100–499 employees
- **Large enterprises:** 500 or more employees

In 2022, **small enterprises accounted for 98%** of all employer businesses in Canada. These small businesses provided employment for **10.3 million people**, which is nearly three times the number of people employed in medium-sized businesses.

SMEs in the European Union

The **European Union (EU)** also provides detailed definitions of what constitutes small and medium-sized enterprises. According to the EU standard:

- **Small enterprises** employ fewer than 50 people,
- **Medium-sized enterprises** employ fewer than 250 people,
- And there are also **micro-enterprises** employing up to 10 people.

As in many other countries, SMEs make up **99% of all businesses** in the European Union. They employ approximately **100 million people** and produce **more than half of the EU's Gross Domestic Product (GDP)**.

SMEs in China

The classification of enterprise size in China is quite complex. Generally, companies are categorized based on their **operating revenue, number of employees, or total assets**.

For example:

- **Retail enterprises** in China are considered small if they employ **10–49 workers** and have **annual revenue of at least USD 1 million**.
- **Real estate developers** are classified as small if they have **annual revenue between USD 1–10 million** and **total assets between USD 20–50 million**.
- **Agricultural enterprises** are small if their **annual operating revenue ranges from USD 0.5–5 million**.

Between **2021 and 2025**, China is expected to make large investments in supporting SMEs. According to the **Ministry of Industry and Information Technology**, there

are currently **over 1 million SMEs** in China, and it is projected that **another 100,000 innovative SMEs** will be established during this period.

Main Findings

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are businesses whose **revenue, assets, or number of employees** remain below a certain threshold. Each country has its own definition of SMEs and may also apply different criteria depending on the sector of activity. SMEs play a **vital role** in the economy by creating employment opportunities and driving innovation.

Governments around the world regularly provide **support measures** for SMEs, including **preferential tax regimes, financial incentives, and improved access to credit**. These policies aim to strengthen the competitiveness and sustainability of small and medium-sized businesses as key drivers of economic growth.

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